

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF QUINCE FRUIT VARIETIES

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Abstract: The article presents the results of an experimental study on the macro- and microelement composition of quince fruits of the Aromatnaya and Izobilnaya varieties grown under the soil and climatic conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the research results, the presence of macro- and microelements such as Ca, K, Na, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Se, and Mo in quince fruits was identified, and recommendations were provided for obtaining functional products from quince fruits.

Introduction. It is well known that the natural climatic conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are highly favorable for the development of horticulture and farming. Consequently, special attention has been given to the enhancement of fruit and vegetable production in the country. As evidence of this focus, one can cite official documents such as the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019, "On the Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030" [1], and the Presidential Resolution dated December 15, 2021, "On Measures to Support the Fruit and Vegetable Sector, and Further Develop the Cluster and Cooperation System in the Industry" [2].

Due to the state-level attention being paid to the cultivation of fruit and vegetable products, the share of fresh fruits and vegetables, as well as their processed products, in the dietary structure of the population is steadily increasing. At the same time, opportunities for exporting these products to numerous foreign countries are also expanding.

Among the sweet and flavorful fruits grown in our country, quince also holds a special place. Quince fruit possesses medicinal properties and is beneficial in the treatment of high blood pressure, eye diseases, and atherosclerosis. In addition, it serves as a powerful remedy against colds and exhibits strong antiseptic properties [3].

It should be noted that although the biology of the widely cultivated quince varieties in our country has been well studied, there has been insufficient scientific research on their biological value, particularly in the production of functional food products based on quince. Therefore, we became interested in investigating which macro and microelements are present in quince fruit.

As the object of research, the fruits of the Aromatnaya and Izobilnaya varieties of quince, grown in the orchards of the Bandixon Horticultural and Viticulture Experimental Farm of the M. Mirziyoyev Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture, and Wine-making of Uzbekistan, were used.

The quantities of macro and microelements were determined using the atomic absorption method on the "Saturn" spectrometer at the Laboratory of the Institute of Biorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The results of the study on the quantities of macro and microelements in quince fruit are presented in the following Table 1.

1- Table

Macro and Microelement Composition of Quince Fruit

T/r	Macro and Microelement	Pomological Varieties of Quince (Cydonia oblonga)	
		Izobilnaya	Aromatnaya
Macroelement Composition of Quince Fruit (mg/100g)			
1.	Ca (Calcium)	170,12	224,95
2.	K (Potassium)	66,03	79,48
3.	S (Sulfur)	20,08	26,51
4.	Fe (Iron)	8,95	12,79
5.	Na (Sodium)	5,56	6,52
6.	Si (Silicon)	5,06	6,53
7.	B (Bor)	0,85	0,61
8.	Al (Aluminum)	0,61	1,02
Microelement Composition of Quince Fruit (mkg/100g)			
9.	Ba (Barium)	36,0	44,3
10.	Sr (Strontium)	99,1	143,6
11.	Ti (Titanium)	131,4	134,5
12.	Cr (Chromium)	51,8	60,9
13.	Cu (Copper)	44,7	53,4
14.	Ga (Gallium)	2,0	2,4
15.	Mo (Molybdenum)	3,9	4,3
16.	Zr (Zirconium)	3,9	6,4
17.	Rb (Rubidium)	25,4	23,9
18.	Se (Selenium)	9,4	14,2
19.	Co (Cobalt)	1,5	2,1
20.	Mn (Manganese)	1,4	2,3
21.	Ni (Nickel)	16,4	20,0

The research results indicate that the accumulation of mineral elements in quince fruit is significantly influenced by the pomological variety of the quince and the growing conditions. For example, when we compared the data we obtained regarding the amounts of macro and microelements in quince fruit with the figures presented in the "Chemical Composition of Food Products Handbook" [4], it was found that the levels of potassium and sodium in quince fruit grown under Uzbekistan's soil and climatic conditions were lower than the figures in the handbook. However, the levels of calcium, iron, and sulfur were considerably higher. For instance, the handbook indicates that the iron content in quince fruit is 3 mg per 100 g of the product. In contrast, in the Izobilnaya variety of quince that we studied, this figure was found to be 8.95 mg/100 g. Additionally, it was found that the Aromatnaya variety of quince is richer in calcium and iron compared to the Izobilnaya variety. These findings highlight the

significant impact of variety and environmental conditions on the mineral composition of quince fruit.

The research results revealed that the quince fruit contains important microelements such as selenium, cobalt, chromium, manganese, molybdenum, and zirconium.

In conclusion, due to its richness in macro and microelements, which are biologically active substances, quince fruit can be used in the production of functional food products that are rich in active compounds.

References:

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